

TWO FACES OF HABITUAL RESIDENCE – A MASTERPIECE OF THE HCCH AND A CHALLENGE

Abstract: *Habitual residence, a pivotal concept in private international law, was conceptualised by the Hague Conference on Private International Law. In an effort to reconcile two disparate legal systems, one favouring nationality as a connecting factor, the other domicile, the Conference proposed a third, neutral option: habitual residence. Guided by the age-old Latin maxim that every definition is perilous – omnis-definitio periculose est, the Conference refrained from defining habitual residence, leaving its interpretation to judicial practice. Over time, habitual residence has evolved into a crucial criterion for determining the applicable law and international jurisdiction in the majority of the Conference's conventions. This paper meticulously traces the evolution of habitual residence across the three periods of the Hague Conference: the first – from its inception to the adoption of the Statute (1893-1951); the second – from the adoption of the Statute to the European Union's accession (1951-2007); and the third – from the European Union's accession to the present day (2007-).*

Keywords: *Habitual residence, the Hage Conference, a masterpiece, a challenge.*

1. Introduction

The genesis of habitual residence and its application in private international law can be traced back to the pioneering work of the Hague Conference on Private International Law. This pivotal term was first employed as early as 1896 in the Hague Convention on Civil Procedure. However, there are assertions that its origins predate this; specifically, it was initially used in a bilateral agreement between France and Prussia in 1880.¹ The author posits that it is a French rendition of the German phrase 'gewöhnliche Aufen-

thalt', encapsulating a precise legal concept.² In literal translation, it denotes a permanent place of residence. However, the habitual residence has a broader scope, particularly through the contributions of the Hague Conference on Private International Law.

Simultaneously, we can trace the dynamic evolution of habitual residence through three distinct periods. The first period is related to the work of the Conference before the Second World War, more precisely from the beginning of work in 1893 to 1951. Out of a total of seven adopted conventions in that time frame, four mention habitual residence. The second period began with adopting the Statute when the Conference established its bodies and became a permanent intergovernmental institution. It lasted until the accession of the European Union to the Conference in 2007. The habitual residence was used in almost every Convention or Protocol adopted from 1951 to 2007, marking a significant period of its development. The third period began in 2007, when the first regional organisation of an economic nature, the European Union, joined the Conference and continues to this day, reflecting the ongoing evolution of this concept. In that period, three instruments were adopted in which habitual residence is used, which will be discussed later.

Throughout these three periods, we can observe the evolution of habitual residence as a decisive factor for determining the applicable law, a crucial aspect in the field of private international law. This determination also extends to the jurisdiction of the court and other authorities when it comes to conventions dealing with the procedure. Notably, habitual residence is not defined in any instrument of the Hague Conference. However, due to its increasingly frequent use, it became clear that judicial practice needs specific instructions, which began to appear in the explanatory reports given with the conventions over time, highlighting the practical implications of this concept.

2. The first period of The Hague Conference - from its inception to the adoption of the statute(1893-1951)

The first conference in The Hague was held in 1893 at the initiative of the Dutch government. Thirteen countries accepted the invitation.³ Three more meetings were held until 1904, and six conventions were adopted in that time frame, so that period is rightly called "la belle époque"⁴ of the

² *Ibid.*

³ Lipstein, K., *One Hundred Years of Hague Conferences on Private International Law*, *International & Comparative Law Quarterly*, 42(3),1993, p.557.

⁴ Van Hoogstraten, M. H., *The United Kingdom Joins an Uncommon Market: The Hague*

HCCH. Of those six conventions, the 1896 Civil Procedure, 1902 Guardianship Convention, 1905 Civil Procedure Convention, and 1905 Deprivation of Civil Rights Convention stand out as significant milestones in the development of the concept of habitual residence.

The Convention on Civil Procedure in 1986, in Article 15, which regulates free legal aid, first mentioned habitual residence. Namely, a certificate or declaration of low financial status must be taken from the competent authorities of the foreigner's habitual residence. The Convention does not provide any definition of habitual residence. Still, it distinguishes between this term and current residence, considering that in the continuation of the same article, it says that if the certificate is not issued by the authority of the foreigner's habitual residence, it will be issued by the authority of his current residence. Based on this, we can conclude that under habitual residence, the authors of the 1986 Convention considered a more permanent place of residence, but different from domicile, bearing in mind that it is mentioned earlier in the text of the Convention. Although borrowed from German law, where it represented a legal issue, habitual residence was not defined in the 1986 Convention. This is how the customary stay entered private international law through the back door, only to become the main criteria in most Hague conventions half a century later.

The Convention on the Guardianship of Minors from 1902, signed by 14 states, was a significant step in the practical application of habitual residence. It was the first instrument to provide for the use of habitual residence as a criterion for determining the applicable law, albeit in a subsidiary role.⁵ This means that the right of habitual residence of minors is applied only when guardianship is not organised or cannot be organised according to the national law of the child. The remaining two conventions of the first period use the habitual residence as a jurisdictional criterion for issuing a certificate of the low financial status of a foreigner⁶ and as a subsidiary criterion of the applicable law.⁷

The "old conventions" mentioned all share the common feature of using national law as the main criterion for determining the applicable law, with

Conference on Private International Law, International & Comparative Law Quarterly, 12(1), 1963, p.150.

⁵ More about the 1902 Guardianship Convention see. Marjanović, S. Đ., *Children Protection in the Hague Conventions on Private International Law*, doctoral dissertation defended at the University of Niš, Faculty of Law, 2014, pp. 12-20.

⁶ 1905 Civil Procedure Convention.

⁷ 1905 Deprivation of Civil Rights Convention.

habitual residence playing a relatively minor role.⁸ International jurisdiction typically rests with national authorities, and local authorities can only act when national authorities are unresponsive. This can be attributed to the fact that the member states of these conventions are continental European countries, reflecting the attitudes of their creators towards the selection of binding points. The context in which these conventions were established should also be taken into account – a period when large empires were striving to maintain their colonial dominance, and the use of *lex nationalis* was expected in that context. Nevertheless, their significance is notable as they paved the way for habitual residence to become a significant point of connection in private international law. Over time, it has evolved into a modern and widely accepted point of attachment, serving as a link between the countries of the European continent and those of the Anglo-Saxon legal system within both the framework of the Hague Conventions and European Union law. Consequently, habitual residence has been incorporated into many national codifications of private international law.

3. The second period of The Hague Conference - from the adoption of the statute to the European Union's accession (1951–2007)

In the second period of HCCH, the concept of habitual residence emerges as a pivotal factor. It not only becomes an unavoidable criterion of jurisdiction (both direct and indirect) and applicable law but also frequently appears as a criterion of the area of application of an instrument or as one of the additional conditions for the application of domestic law.⁹ This underscores the profound significance of habitual residence, which is found in as many as 26 instruments of the second period, including 25 conventions and one protocol. While it's impractical to delve into each convention, we will focus on those that marked a significant shift in the understanding and application of habitual residence.

⁸ At one time, the old conventions were described as follows: „... „Let nationality be our connecting factor; a man's status was to be governed by his national law as long as he lived and wherever he went.“...“ Van Hoogstaten.M. H. (1963). *op.cit.*,p.151.

⁹ E.g. Convention of 14 March 1978 on Celebration and Recognition of the Validity of Marriages or Convention of 4 May 1971 on the Law Applicable to Traffic Accidents.

3.1. Convention of 15 June 1955 on the law applicable to international sales of goods

Habitual residence assumes the role of a criterion for determining the applicable law.¹⁰ This convention, while lacking a direct definition of habitual residence, is noteworthy for being the first to allude to the habitual residence of a legal person (albeit indirectly, through the mention of the seller's habitual residence, who may be a legal person). In essence, this convention serves as a cornerstone for the concept of the habitual residence of a legal entity, as well as the rule that the habitual residence of a legal entity is deemed to be the location of its representative office if the contract is concluded within the scope of that office's operations. This approach will have profound implications on subsequent Hague Conventions, EU regulations, and national codifications worldwide.

3.2. Convention of 5 October 1961 concerning the powers of authorities and the law applicable in respect of the protection of infants

This Convention, crucially, pertains to the safeguarding of infants' persons and property. Article 1 empowers the judicial and administrative authorities of the state where the infant habitually resides to enact all necessary measures for their protection. These measures are to be in accordance with the laws of the country of the child's habitual residence, as dictated by its internal law.¹¹ However, it's important to note that the jurisdiction to implement protective measures for the infant is primarily influenced by the stance of the state of their nationality.

Like the previous Hague Conventions, the 1961 Convention does not define habitual residence, although other instructions can be found in its text, such as the concept of infant. This again means that it is left to the courts and other competent authorities to interpret the concept of habitual residence by being "inspired by the very spirit of the Convention, i.e. the best interest of the child".¹² However, we can find some guidelines for determining habitual residence in the Explanatory Report for the first time. Thus, as one of the determining elements, the effective centre of the infant's life is mentioned,

¹⁰ Convention of 15 June 1955 on the Law Applicable to International Sales of Goods, art. 2 and 3.

¹¹ Convention of 5 October 1961 Concerning the Powers of Authorities and the Law Applicable in Respect of the Protection of Infants, art. 2.

¹² Steiger, W., Rapport explicatif, w: *Actes et documents de la Neuvième session (1960)*, t. IV: *Protection des mineurs*, 1961, p. 11.

which should be especially valued in other places where the child resides. As another element, the length of stay in a place is indicated, which is also of great importance for the competent authority (but it should not be decisive, for the simple reason that even an extended stay in a place, for example, a sanatorium or an educational institution, cannot be a habitual residence if the infant still has strong and severe ties to another place). In the end, the authors state that deciding on the place of residence of infants must be subordinated to enabling the maximum protection of the child's interests, a principle of utmost importance.¹³

3.3. Convention of 1 June 1970 on the recognition of divorces and legal separations

Habitual residence, in addition to nationality,¹⁴ is a criteria of indirect jurisdiction in the Convention on the Recognition of Divorce and Legal Separations. It is a complex norm that allows for alternative solutions, and one cannot talk about the possible advantage of one of them, for example, the law of habitual residence over nationality. The Convention introduces a third criterion, domicile. In cases where the country of origin uses the concept of domicile as a criterion of jurisdiction in divorce and legal separation, the term 'habitual residence' from Article 2 is understood to include domicile.¹⁵

The Explanatory Report's authors make a significant assertion, stating that „habitual residence would have to be defined only about two questions of pure fact: living within the territory of the State in question and doing so more or less permanently. In the case of several residences in different countries, it will not always be possible to decide which is the habitual residence without going into the question of intent to see which of the residences is habitual or the most habitual of them.“¹⁶ This marks the first time that the element of intention has been attributed to habitual residence, a crucial development in this field.

3.4. Convention of 25 October 1980 on the civil aspects of international child abduction

Habitual residence in this Convention has multiple roles. First of all, it represents a criterion for choosing the applicable law, according to which it

¹³ *Ibid.*, 14.

¹⁴ Convention of 1 June 1970 on the Recognition of Divorces and Legal Separations, art. 2.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, art. 3, para. 1.

¹⁶ Bellet. P., Goldman. B., *Convention on the Recognition of the Divorces and Legal Separations - Draft Adopted By the Eleventh Session and Explanatory Report (English Translation)*, The Hague: Permanent Bureau of the Conference, 1971, p.11.

will be assessed whether the right to care has been violated,¹⁷ and then determines the jurisdiction of the Central Executive Authority to which the injured person or institution submits a request for the return of the child, as well as the competent court that should resolve the issue of custody rights. At the same time, the habitual residence, in most cases, also determines where the child should be returned. However, this is not strictly defined by the Convention, given that there may be cases where the person whose right to care has been violated by removal or detention does not live more in the country of the child's habitual residence.¹⁸

The Hague Convention on the Civil Legal Aspects of International Child Abduction does not contain any closer description of the habitual residence nor guidelines that would guide the courts when deciding on this, which was later characterised as the most significant omission of this Convention.¹⁹ However, valid arguments in support of opposing opinions can be read in the literature.²⁰ The Explanatory Report attached to this Convention states that it is a "long-established" concept within the Hague Conference that refers to pure facts, distinguishing it from the domicile concept.²¹ It does not contain anything that could help determine the child's habitual residence because it does not consider the concept of habitual residence as a disputed issue and, therefore, does not deal with it separately. However, it later turned out that it was not such a naive, implicit matter because the habitual residence „created complicated questions regarding interpretation for judges".²² Thus,

¹⁷ That is, whether it is a wrongful removal or retention.

¹⁸ Pérez-Vera, E., *Explanatory Report on the 1980 Hague Child Abduction Convention*, Netherlands: HCCH Publications, 1982, pp. 459-460.

¹⁹ Silberman, L., *Interpreting the Hague Abduction Convention: In Search of a Global Jurisprudence*, ILLJ Working Paper, 5, 2005, p. 14.

²⁰ Gallagher, E., *A House Is Not (Necessarily) a Home: A Discussion of the Common Law Approach to Habitual Residence*, NYUJ Int'l L. & Pol., 2014, p.498. The author believes that defining the Habitual place of residence in this Convention would perhaps make the job easier in some cases, but because of that, many children who fall under the so-called atypical cases remained unprotected. The refusal to define habitual residence has allowed the courts to do what is best for the child in each particular case by allowing them to consider all the relevant facts. In this way, courts create standards that best suit each legal system.

²¹ Pérez-Vera, E. *op.cit.*, p.445. However, the idea that it is a well-known term has met with numerous criticisms. Among other things, it is stated that before the Hague Convention on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction, there were not many cases in which the courts had to determine habitual residence, and that the idea that the two words «habitual» and «residence» are quite sufficient to understand this concept, unsustainable. See about that. Schuz, R., *Disparity and the Quest for Uniformity in Implementing the Hague Abduction Convention*, J. Comp. L., 9, 3., 2014, pp. 6-7.

²² Silberman, L. J., *Cooperative Efforts in Private International Law on Behalf of Children:*

there is no agreement whether, when determining the child's habitual residence, the emphasis should be on the child or whether the intentions of his parents/guardians should be taken into account, or primarily the intentions of the parents/guardians. Even within the same country, in the USA, there are three different views: according to the first, the emphasis is strictly on the child;²³ according to the second, only the intention of the parent/guardian is taken into account,²⁴ while the third approach is a combination of the previous two.²⁵

These differences come to the fore, especially regarding family relocation, because the factual circumstances may indicate different types of relocation - permanent, temporary, for a certain period, etc. The problem is whether the habitual residence, which refers to the place where a person has his or her permanent home, is lost immediately after the move, if it is a move for an indefinite period, or if a certain period elapses. In addition, in the case of temporary relocations, it is unclear whether the previous habitual residence is retained or a new one is acquired. Finally, it is questionable whether it is possible to acquire habitual residence in the new country in case of relocation for a determined period. The answers depend, as a rule, on the interpretation of the intention as a subjective element, given that, a stay of six months can be characterised as a habitual residence, while a stay of three years in a new country does not have to be an obstacle to keeping the old one habitual residence.

Therefore, it is evident that the claim that the use of habitual residence is a "well-known establishment" is debatable because it opens the way for the courts to interpret this term as they see fit. The consequence is that the reason for refusing to return the child is most often stated as the child not having a habitual residence in the country that requested the return. However, despite these differences in interpretation, we firmly believe that it was the 1980 Convention, a pivotal legal instrument, that brought the concept of habitual residence to the forefront of legal science and practice.

3.5. Convention of 1 August 1989 on the law applicable to succession to the estates of deceased persons

The purpose of this convention is to standardise the rules on the governing law for the inheritance of the property of deceased persons. It does

The Hague Children's Conventions, Paris: Martinus Nijhoff, 2006, p. 346.

²³ Case *Freidrich v. Freidrich*, 983 F.2d 1396, 125 ALR Fed. 703 (6th Cir. 1993), INCADAT HC/Udf 142.

²⁴ Case *Ruiz v. Tenorio*, 392 F.3d 1247 (11th Cir. 2004), INCADAT HC/E/Usf 780.

²⁵ Case *Feder v. Evans-Feder*, 63 F.3d 217 (2d Cir. 1995), INCADAT HC/E/Usf 83.

not regulate the form of disposition, testamentary capacity, matters related to marital property, or property transfer in another way.

The Convention does not define the concept of habitual residence in more detail, but we find a more detailed explanation in the Explanatory Report. As stated, „the habitual residence is determined by a more equal weighting of a range of elements. Essentially, it is the place of belonging of the *de cuius*. A person can have only one habitual residence because it is the centre of his living, the place with which he is most closely associated in his pattern of life. His family and personal ties are essential to determining this place. The intention appears to play a more muted role as an element in habitual residence than it traditionally has done in domicile, and this is why lawyers who are accustomed to working with domicile as a connecting factor hesitate before accepting the term, habitual residence as an equivalent, but finally, accept it as a possible alternative. It is a regular physical presence, enduring for some time, and a stronger association than ‘ordinary’ or ‘simple’ residence, of which the *de cuius* may have had two or more. However, the manifest hopes and plans of the *de cuius* are also elements that may be legitimately considered by the person who would have to know which State is the habitual residence.”²⁶ Therefore, to say that an individual has a habitual residence in a place, in addition to his regular presence, his circumstances, such as family, hopes and plans, are also important.

3.6. Convention of 29 May 1993 on protection of children and cooperation in respect of intercountry adoption

Habitual residence in this Convention is one of the conditions for applying the Convention. The Convention does not define the concept of habitual residence, nor does it determine how it is determined. However, over time, several problems arose in connection with habitual residence, precisely within the scope of the Convention, such as determining the habitual residence of workers on the so-called temporary work abroad who appear in the role of adoptive parents. The question of the habitual residence of persons whose centre of life is in one country but living in a neighbouring country and the question of adoption by persons who changed their habitual residence during the adoption procedure is open. In addition to the questions mentioned above regarding the habitual residence of potential adopters, two doubts arose regarding the habitual residence of the child, i.e. adoptee. The first concerns the habitual residence of a child who was born in a coun-

²⁶ Waters. D. W. M., *Explanatory Report on the 1989 Hague Succession Convention. Proceedings of the Sixteenth Session (1988), tome II – Succession to estates, applicable law*, The Hague: Permanent Bureau of the Conference, 1988, p. 549.

try shortly after his mother arrived in that country. It is debatable whether this is an attempt to abuse the mother and the child, in the sense of deliberately moving them immediately before giving birth, to a member state so that the Convention can be applied. It is a matter of selling the child or some other (illegal) behaviour that could cause harm to the child. Another doubt relates to the situation when a child is adopted who temporarily lives in the country of habitual residence of the potential adopters. The main problem is whether it is a domestic or international adoption, which will directly depend on whether the child has kept his former habitual residence or acquired a new one in the country where he temporarily but currently resides, which is at the same time the country of habitual residence of potential adopters. For this reason, specific rules for determining habitual residence to apply this Convention have crystallised over time:

- no single factor is determinative;
- the various factors must be weighed and, depending on the specific circumstances;
- each factor will not always be given the same relative weight in the determination of habitual residence and
- greater caution is necessary when the time spent in the country is relatively short.²⁷

4. The third period of The Hague Conference - from the European Union's accession to the present day (2007-)

The habitual residence appears in three instruments of this period: the Convention of 23 November 2007 on the International Recovery of Child Support and Other Forms of Family Maintenance, the Protocol of 23 November 2007 on the Law Applicable to Maintenance Obligations, and the Convention of 2 July 2019 on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Judgments in Civil or Commercial Matters.

Habitual residence is the criterion of indirect jurisdiction in the first-mentioned instrument. The Convention provides a “partial”²⁸ definition of habitual residence. In Article 9, it is clarified that the request for recognition

²⁷ Note on Habitual Residence and the Scope of the 1993 Hague Convention on Protection of Children and Co-operation in Respect of Intercountry Adoption. Retrieved May 21, 2024, from <https://assets.hcch.net/docs/12255707-4d23-4f90-a819-5e759d0d7245.pdf>.

²⁸ Borrás, A., & Degeling, J., *Convention of 23 november 2007 on the international recovery of child support and other forms of family maintenance. Explanatory report*, URL: <https://assets.hcch.net/upload/expl38>. р(дата звернення: 31.01. 2021), 2009, р.73.

of a decision is to be submitted through the central authority of the contracting state where the applicant resides to the central authority of the state of recognition. This provision excludes „mere presence“ from the definition of residence. Therefore, „mere presence“ is not considered residence because residence implies a stronger connection between the individual and the territory. In this context, habitual residence is seen as a more significant link than residence, which can sometimes be to the detriment of the Convention's purpose.²⁹

The Protocol on the Law Applicable to Maintenance Obligations confirms that habitual residence is a more stable concept than residence. The mere presence of a temporary nature is insufficient to determine the governing law for maintenance obligations.³⁰ The length of stay in a particular place is emphasised, so a stay, e.g., for education or some temporary activity, is not considered a habitual residence.³¹

Regarding the third-mentioned instrument, in which habitual residence is one of the criteria for indirect jurisdiction, it is interesting that its third article, which contains definitions of specific terms, states the following: „An entity or person other than a natural person shall be considered to be habitually resident in the State – (a) where it has its statutory seat; (b) under the law of which it was incorporated or formed; (c) where it has its central administration; or (d) where it has its principal place of business.“ (article 3, paragraph 2). The criteria based on which the subject's habitual residence is determined are alternatively set so that it can be any of these places. The Explanatory Report states that the criteria are not set hierarchically, nor are they mutually exclusive, which means that if the subject has, by Article 3, a habitual residence in several countries at the same time, any of those places can be considered his habitual residence, for application of this Convention.³²

²⁹ The US delegation suggested that residence be defined to include habitual residence but exclude mere presence. This would facilitate the recognition and enforcement of maintenance decisions. About that see: Proposal by delegation of the United States of America, regarding Chapter I (Scope and definitions) of Preliminary Document No. 16. Retrieved May 21, 2024, from https://assets.hcch.net/upload/wop/comments38_us.pdf.

³⁰ Bonomi, A., *Protocol of 23 November 2007 on the Law Applicable to Maintenance Obligations: Explanatory Report*, The Hague: The Permanent Bureau, 2013, p. 49.

³¹ *Ibid.*

³² Garcimartín, F., & Saumier, G., *Convention of 2 July 2019 on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Judgments in Civil or Commercial Matter*, 2020, p. 77.

5. Conclusion

Much more space would be needed to at least approximate the contribution of the Hague Conference to the development of habitual residence as a point of attachment. However, due to the limitations regarding the scope of the work, we were forced to mention only the most significant conventions, which, in a way, represented a kind of guide to the interpretation of the Habitual residence. The very fact that habitual residence is used in over 30 instruments of the Hague Conference, that today it dominates the international private law of the European Union, as well as that it represents an unavoidable binding point in numerous national systems of private international law, speaks in favour of the fact that it is genuinely a masterpiece The Hague Conference. As far back as 1893, it predicted that the notions of domicile and citizenship would be overcome in the modern world and far from representing the closest connection between one person and one territory.

We will not find a definition of this term in any of the conventions. Namely, the Hague Conference resisted the challenge of defining it over the years, although today, such definitions can be found in domestic codifications. It may seem that the opportunity to adopt a unique definition of this often-used criterion of applicable law and judicial jurisdiction was missed. However, practical experience demonstrates that doubts related to the determination of habitual residence can be overcome, and the lack of a formal definition does not negate its significance as a point of attachment.

Summary

Habitual residence is a concept created by the Hague Conference on Private International Law. To reconcile two polarised legal systems, one of which preferred nationality as a connecting factor and the other, which used domicile, the Hague Conference offered a third, neutral solution: habitual residence. Guided by the old Latin maxim that every definition is dangerous – *omnis definitio periculose est*, the Conference did not define habitual residence but left its interpretation to judicial practice. Over time, habitual residence has become a necessary criterion for determining the applicable law and international jurisdiction in most of its conventions.

Today, habitual residence is the decisive connecting factor in the PIL of the EU and the national PIL systems of an increasing number of states. Perhaps the most significant thing is that in recent national codifications of PIL, uniform solutions have been offered regarding the status, family, inheritance and obligation law. All this is thanks to the habitual residence. We can

talk about the beginning of the creation of unified Private International Law, made by the states through their national codifications. In the outcome, this could result in establishing “International Private International Law”, with the remaining minor differences of a national character. So, it would not be wrong to call the habitual residence a kind of masterpiece of the Hague Conference.

On the other, the unequal interpretation of habitual residence represented one of the biggest challenges for the Hague Conference. There seem to have been no problems until 1983, when the Child Abduction Convention entered into force. It became apparent that specific dilemmas arose regarding determining a person’s habitual residence. Also, some other questions were raised, starting with its constituent elements, methods of acquisition, and loss, through to whether it is possible for a person to have no habitual residence at all or even to have more than one habitual residence.

In addition to the general concept of habitual residence, the Hague Conference also created its particular forms: habitual residence of a legal entity, habitual residence of a child and habitual residence of the *de cujus*. The paper describes the development of habitual residence through the three periods of the Hague Conference: the first – from the foundation to the adoption of the Statute (1893-1951); the second one – from the adoption of the Statute to the accession of the European Union (1951-2007) and the third one – from the accession of the European Union until the present day (2007-).

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